

Materials included in scoping exercise in development of initial programme theories

Academic Papers

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CPT Programmes

1. CPT programme co-delivered by YF, RMcM and trainers with aphasia to speech and language therapy students at university of Galway, Ireland. This programme is based on a CPT programme that was developed at Connect, the communication disability network (McVicker et al., 2009).
2. KomTil – A danish programme described by Isaksen et al., (2023, p.174) as follows: “a program for healthcare professionals working with people with aphasia in all rehabilitation phases, developed as a part of a project in 2017–2020 to improve the care pathway for people with aphasia in the Southwest of Denmark (Bertram et al., 2021). KomTil was co-designed with people with aphasia, relatives, healthcare professionals, and researchers and is inspired by other communication partner training programs (e.g. Kagan et al., 2001)”

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